

Paper 5

**INNOVATIVE AND CREATIVE TEACHING TO
STIMULATE PARTICIPATION OF STUDENTS AT
HIGHER EDUCATION FOR SOCIAL CHANGE**

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Abstract

“Human existence depends upon compassion and curiosity leading to knowledge, but curiosity and knowledge without compassion is inhuman and compassion without curiosity and knowledge is ineffectual”. – Victor Weisskopf, nuclear physicist [Shapiro, 2011]. Yet one of the most important and difficult jobs in the world is teaching. In education, student participation refers to the degree of attention, curiosity, interest, optimism and passion that students show when they are learning, or being taught. This extends to the level of motivation that they have to learn and progress in their education.

1. RESEARCH PROBLEM

How can we as educators nurture students of design Institute to be good future engaged citizens for sustainable development of the society.

1. OBJECTIVE

This paper aims to discuss the fact that responsibility towards the society needs to be inculcated through education system into the mindset of the students to prepare them to be good citizens for the betterment of the community as a whole. We as educators have the key role not only to develop knowledge but also to promote a social responsibility culture.

Secondly, through explorative case studies, the involvement of students in social change is brought forth.

We also determine some obstacles faced while promoting and initiating such initiatives.

3. VIEWS AND DEFINITIONS

The philosopher John Dewey wrote, "Education is not a preparation for life but life itself." He believed that classrooms aren't just places to study social change, but a place to spark social change.

Socrates himself said, "Education is a kindling of a flame, not the filling of a vessel". It then follows that using Socrates' method of discourse as a teaching tool will line-up well with Dewey's goals for the classrooms. Design education is no exception.

According to Plato, the purpose of education is to cultivate the intellect, pursued for its own sake, in order to uncover the universal themes and natural laws that the prepared mind can discern beneath the surface confusion of life. (Berman, 1990)

Socrates states, the purpose of an education is to prepare citizens to participate in public affairs. (Berman, 1990).

Change is an inevitable law of life. Change should by all means happen for good. "What you leave behind is not what is woven into lives of others". – Pericles (circa 495-429 BCE), the most promising and prominent Greek statesman.

Aristotle states, "Educating the mind without educating the heart is no education at all" So how do we as educators, bring change in the society for the betterment of life?

Social Responsibility is an ethical framework and suggests that an entity be it an organization or individual has an obligation to act for the benefit of society at a large.

"Be the change that you want to see in the world" as stated by Gandhiji. "The world is moved along, not only by the mighty shoves of its heroes, but also by the aggregate of tiny pushes of each honest worker – "Helen Keller".

"We need to help young people recognize their own capacity to do good, and help them discover the rewards of generosity" – Bill Clinton. Social responsibility is a personal investment in the well-being of others and the planet [Berman, 1990].

Social responsibility of education is a process whereby the whole community transmits to the next generation appropriate values, traditions, skills and cultural norms. Service learning not only promotes good deeds but also academic success.

2. METHODOLOGY

As the paper aims to discuss the fact that social responsibility needs to be inculcated in the students through education system, the focus group are students of Design School of Fourth

Year. The number of students is 54. The focus of the task is to observe and understand the participation and creative output of the students towards various social issues identified by them.

Students were encouraged to identify a problem around them which needed attention. They were further led towards research regarding the social issue. They moved out of the classrooms, mixed with their target group, interviewed them; spend time with them to understand the root cause of the problem and the expectations of the target group. Later several brainstorming sessions were conducted; problem solving processes were carried out, material exploration done to narrow down upon ways to resolve the problem. Then companies were approached to carry out a docket project with the CSR funds of the companies.

5.DISCUSSION

Students' participation in any noble cause had always been and will always continue in future.

STUDENTS' PARTICIPATION IN INDIAN FREEDOM MOVEMENT

During the struggle for independence in India, the youth had actively participated which is noteworthy. They had selflessly taken up the leadership and contributed immensely, plunged into the streets protesting the wrong governance of the British rule. During participation of Bengal in 1905, the young students were in the leadership to protest against the British, all for a social cause, political freedom of the motherland. The whole world is aware of the contribution of young freedom fighters Khudiram Bose, Bhagat Singh, Chandra Shekhar Azad, Bagha Jatin, Subhash Chandra Bose and innumerable more, in the freedom struggle.

Students of various socio-cultural backgrounds come together in the institutions. Out of India's total population projected close to 1.37 billion [Ministry of Statistics and Programme Implementation, Government of India, 2017], 34.6 million are enrolled into higher education. [All India Survey on Higher Education, 2015-16, Govt. of India, Ministry of Human Resource Development, Dept. of Higher Education]. The future of our country is in their hands. So if we as educators can motivate them to participate in social responsible projects, we see immense scope of prospective students who can develop the future of our country into a sustained and empathetic environment. Youth force is dynamic in nature as many skills are developed during this period.

Social empathy and responsibility of social well-being should be nurtured right from the early childhood days, ie. from school level, like keeping the surrounding clean, helping others, hygienic habits like washing of hands before food, cover the mouth while coughing or planting trees for a greener environment, not wasting food, etc. this is also a part of the curriculum in environmental science, moral values etc. The young students at school follow the instructions and acts accordingly. But, when the child reaches higher education, he is matured enough and has his own developed ideas. He has his set of understandings and beliefs. He now focuses more on his own well-being and the whole world is a competition now. He has immense energy ready

to be channelized. So interception at this point of time is very necessary to guide them to understand their responsibilities, not only towards themselves, their family but the society as a whole. They can achieve bigger goals (towards society) along with academics and career. They can be leaders of social change. This realization can only be fostered within them by the teachers through various curriculums and projects.

In any formal education system, most learning activities take place in classrooms. It is an important context where both students and instructor come into contact to share information in their quest of knowledge. Teachers and students are the two major stakeholders in Higher Education System. Teachers are believed to be the key actors and agents of social change. It is a long drawn debate that whether teachers should be tasked to preparing students to confirm or to actively push for progress and improvement where there is necessary.

It is therefore a challenge to inculcate awareness, social responsibility and leadership well in the minds since the formative years by sensitizing them about social issues. This is a renewed concern for educators of today. Nurturing their talents and interests to address various aspects of social responsibility, co-operative learning, developing morals, thus leading them towards global education is the primary focus.

TEACHER'S RESPONSIBILITY TO STIMULATE SOCIAL PARTICIPATION

The teacher needs to open a window regarding the problems pertaining to the society; to be informed about the problem is the first step towards solving it.

6.ACCEPT THE RELATIONSHIP WITH SOCIETY

With today's classroom curriculum the complete focus is on self-development. The student just tries to excel in academics. On the contrary, our goal should be holistic development of the students. Teachers should make them realize that they are a part of a greater community and understand and accept their responsibility towards it. The self-realization of responsibility will build an empathetic outlook in the students. Students prefer hands-on activities and to get to collaborate with their peers.

In the Case study carried out, the focus group was given a task to explore and study problems in the society which needed immediate attention. They moved out of the classroom, interviewed people, did some surveys and finally came up with very interesting problems which caught their attention.

Some of the interesting problems traced by the students are as follows:

- Children in slums suffer illness due to germs that go to their body through food, because they do not wash their hands before eating.
- Spitting on roads and on the walls, thinking it is dirty anyways. This causes a dirty and unhygienic environment as many germs are transmitted by spit.

- Increased rate of crime in youth due to lack of Emotion Management and influence of violence in movies.
- Plight of farmers of Vidharva districts of Maharashtra
- Water logging problems in Mumbai during rains.
- After festivals, Idols are immersed in the water resources. Idols being made of plaster-of-paris do not dissolve and cause pollution and kills water-life.
- Lack of education or learning help to poor kids or kids of domestic help.

There were several problems that were identified. After identification of the problems, brainstorming and research, a unique and creative design solution was derived for each.

Options of clay idols with seeds embedded in them, which can be re-turned to the soil. Seeds embedded in-turn would germinate into new plants thus helping in developing a green environment. Adopting BMC primary schools and taking out a little time to teach a poor child, as an extension of 'each one teach one' initiative would help the society immensely. While adopting schools, the premises were painted thematically for children to encourage them and give them a happy environment for learning. Teaching kids through animated story-telling sessions about the importance of washing hands before eating or other hygienic habits, judicious use of plastic, designing app for support of youth who are suffering from emotional management issues with the use of technology. These were some of the very creative solutions proposed by students of a design school. It made them aware of the society and connected them to the needs and problems around them.

What they learned from the project:

- ▶ Create leadership development opportunities and foster a commitment to social and civic responsibilities
- ▶ Exploring real world issues
- ▶ Motivate students to be empathetic towards social causes and encourage them to think of innovative and creative approaches
- ▶ Developing participatory activities and social skills
- ▶ Experiments related to social responsibility
- ▶ Build a co-ordination with industry experts to join hands with students for social cause.

Students can be motivated to participate in various types of social responsibility activities like:

- Environment sustainability activities
- Direct philanthropic giving
- Spreading knowledge and education
- Ethical business practice and

- Help in empowerment by building entrepreneurship
- Fund raising activities
- Help to eradicate substance abuse
- Health, hygiene and sanitation activities
- Cleanliness drives
- Drives to fight taboos with scientific logic and train the society to think likewise
- Product development for sustainable society and emergencies and manufacture with minimum cost or from refused material.

Some innovative teaching techniques and strategies that can be implemented:

- Inquiry based learning. This technique triggers curiosity in students. The teachers in this case act as facilitators.
- QR codes. For quick response, QR codes can be developed in the study material for quick response. It can lead students to information just by scanning the code on a students' digital device.
- Problem or project based learning (PBL). This system develops deeper learning competencies. Students are introduced to using real world scenarios, challenges and problems thus engaging students in critical thinking, problem solving, team work and self-management.
The problems students solve can be presented to community leaders to solve problems in actual society. Hence, collaborative project based learning (PBL) is actually helping to bring social change and the major stakeholders, teachers and students functioning as the actual agents of the social change. Thus, PBL techniques connect students and institutes to the real worlds.
- Wisely managed classroom technology. ICT in education, digital tools and problem solving skills will help to connect more with these real-time projects.

Challenges faced by students during the experimentation

- ▶ Lack of information
- ▶ Not able to reach target group
- ▶ Obstacles from parents
- ▶ Pressure of classroom curriculum
- ▶ Lack of funds
- ▶ Challenge of creative output

7. CONCLUSION:

As Rabindranath Tagore states in his poetry “Let My Country Awake” to inspire individual and social change: “Into the heaven of freedom my father, let my country awake”. Let our country awake in a tomorrow where today’s youth has taken and lead responsibility to eradicate social problems, into a world of free and global learning sensitization, innovative teaching, sustainable development.

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